

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: Laying hen, pullet

Level: Husbandry

Keywords: Behaviour, Enrichment, Housing system, Management

Background context provided by the requestor

Piling behaviour of poultry leading to mortalities is a major welfare problem for pullets and laying hens. Research projects regarding the causes have already been carried out. What is missing are practical solutions to prevent piling behaviour.

Question raised by the requestor

Are there field solutions, recommendations, good practices that can be implemented in housing of pullets and laying hens to prevent piling?

Answer

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (the Centre) launched in February 2025 one survey for competent authorities and one for farmers regarding piling behaviour, with the aim to find good practices already implemented in European farms to avoid piling behaviour. However, the Centre only received one answer to these surveys, which impairs recommendations of field solutions or good practices.

[Query n° 2024-007](#) largely discusses the scientific knowledge available regarding piling behaviour, including definition, causes, consequences and practical solutions. The Centre is not able to provide additional recommendations to those already provided in this previous query.

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